

A hardware implementation of CCSDS 122.1-B-1 for transformed-based multispectral and hyperspectral image compression

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Abstract

Nowadays, multispectral and hyperspectral imaging is a key remote sensing technology used in Earth observation missions for commercial, scientific and defense/security applications. The explosive growth in hyperspectral image data volume and instrument data rates, compete with limited available on-board storage resources and downlink bandwidth, making hyperspectral and multispectral image data compression a mission critical task. Lossy compression allows to achieve significant compression gains as a tradeoff to some distortion between the reconstructed and the original image. The CCSDS-122.1-B-1 Recommended standard, extends CCSDS 122.0-B-2 standard for compression of monoband two-dimensional (2D) images by providing an effective method of encoding multispectral and hyperspectral image data, specifying certain spectral transforms to exploit the similarities between the spectral bands, creating a transformed image that it is more efficiently compressed by the 2D encoders. In this paper, we introduce a hardware architecture and implementation of the CCSDS 122.1 standard. The introduced hardware architecture was described in VHDL and implemented, validated and demonstrated on a commercially available Zynq-7000 SoC ZC706 Evaluation Kit development board hosting a Xilinx XC7Z045 SRAM FPGA achieving a throughput performance of 1.5 Gbps. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first hardware implementation of CCSDS 122.1-B-1 Recommended standard in the open literature, thus offering a hardware-accelerated solution for transformed-based lossy multispectral and hyperspectral image compression.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral imaging is recognized as a cornerstone remote sensing technology. The explosive growth in hyperspectral image data volume (several TBs per orbit) compete with limited available on-board storage resources and downlink bandwidth, making hyperspectral image data compression a mission critical on-board data processing task. Lossy compression allows to achieve significant compression gains as a tradeoff to some distortion between the reconstructed and the original image.

The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS), initially, in 2005 approved CCSDS 122.0-B-1 as the Recommended standard for Image Data Compression (IDC). CCSDS-IDC defined a particular transform-based image data compression algorithm providing both lossless and lossy (both rate and quality limited) compression, suitable for monoband two-dimensional (2D) images. CCSDS-IDC consists of a spatial discrete wavelet transform (DWT), which is then followed by a bit-plane coder (BPE). The CCSDS-122.1-B-1 Recommended standard, “Spectral Preprocessing Transform for Multispectral and Hyperspectral Image Compression” issued in 2017, extends CCSDS-IDC by providing an effective method of encoding multispectral and hyperspectral image data, specifying certain spectral transforms to exploit the similarities between the spectral bands, creating a transformed image that it is more efficiently compressed by the 2D encoders. To provide compatibility between the 122.0 (IDC) and 122.1 standards, a second issue of 122.0 (CCSDS 122.0-B-2) was also released in 2017, as well. Contrary to CCSDS 123.0-B-2 which is a low complexity prediction-based “near-lossless” compressor that provides a user-specified guarantee on Peak Absolute Error, the transform-based CCSDS-122.1-B-1 algorithm is a much more complex algorithm designed to reduce distortion in an average sense, rather than limit it on a per-sample basis. The CCSDS-122.1-B-1 transform-based method has a higher chance of outperforming the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 predictive approach when either compressed data rate is relatively low (not close to lossless), spectral bands are highly correlated and there are a large number of bands for the transform to exploit.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of the CCSDS-122.1-B-1 compressor. Source: [1]

In this contribution, we introduce a hardware architecture and implementation of the CCSDS 122.1 standard. The introduced hardware architecture was described in VHDL and it was implemented, validated and demonstrated on a commercially available Zynq-7000 SoC ZC706 Evaluation Kit development board hosting a Xilinx XC7Z045 SRAM FPGA. A SpaceFibre serial link interface IP Core provided by ESA and a ISAFT SpaceFibre EGSE platform provided by TELETEL were used for the demonstration. Although the demonstrator utilized a FPGA SoC suitable for CubeSat and New Space applications, the proposed architecture can be easily ported to target Xilinx Radiation-Tolerant Kintex UltraScale XQRKU060 space-grade devices. The CCSDS 122.1 hardware implementation was validated against a CCSDS 122.1 golden reference model provided by CNES under NDA. The introduced CCSDS 122.1 system achieves a throughput performance of 1.5 Gbps. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first hardware implementation of CCSDS 122.1-B-1 Recommended standard in the open literature.

The rest of this contribution is organized as follows: Section 2 provides background information about the CCSDS-122.1-B-1 Recommended Standard. Section 3 describes the introduced architecture for all subsystems. Section 4 provides implementation results including FPGA resources and throughput performance. Section 5 describes the verification, validation and demonstration platform which is based on the Zynq-7000 SoC ZC706 Evaluation Kit development board interfacing with SpaceFibre IP Core and test equipment. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 BACKGROUND

The structure of CCSDS 122.1 based compressor according to the Recommended standard is depicted in Figure 1. The lossless and lossy hyperspectral compressor consists of two main functional parts: a spectral transform and a set of 2D encoders.

The spectral transform exploits similarities between spectral bands to produce transformed images that can be more efficiently compressed by the 2D encoders. Users can select one of four applicable spectral transform algorithms with different complexities, rate-distortion performance and ability for lossless compression. The defined spectral decorrelators include: a) the identity transform that was defined in order to completely omit the spectral transform stage, b) an Integer Wavelet Transform (IWT) which is the same Cohen–Daubechies–Feauveau (CDF) 5/3 biorthogonal wavelet transform as in JPEG2K but with fixed 5 stages which provides lossless compression and enables high throughput performance through deep pipelining without requiring external memory access, c) the Pairwise Orthogonal Transform (POT) which is an approximation of the excellent Karhunen Loève Transform (KLT) and although has much less computational performance than KLT, it much more complex than IWT demanding multiple cycles-per-sample and requires external memory access that increase latency and lower throughput performance while it is susceptible to discontinuity artifacts d) the Arbitrary Affine Transform (AAT) that cannot provide lossless compression.

Each transformed spectral band is independently compressed by a 2D encoder according to CCSDS 122.0-B-2 (IDC) Recommended standard. The compressed segments produced by the 2D encoders can be interleaved to produce the compressed bit stream. According to the Recommended standard, lossy compression parameters can be adjusted so that to provide both quality-limited or rate-limited compression. Rate-limited compression is controlled by the *SegByteLimit* parameter of CCSDS 122.0-B-2. Using the same compressed rate for each spectral band yields poor performance, thus a rate-allocation method to assign a different compressed data rate to each 2D encoder should be used. Although CCSDS 122.1 does not mandate any particular rate-allocation method allowing the users to choose any desired strategy, it cites three different rate optimization algorithms that vary in complexity and performance that can be employed or modified by the user according the specific application, in order to allocate a fixed bitrate budget among spectral transformed images, codes segments or subsets of coded segments.

Furthermore, upshift and downshift operations facilitate the reuse of existing hardware implementations of the spectral transform and the 2D encoders by limiting the maximum bit depth of the input image to them. Upshift scales an image by a power of two increasing the image bit depth of the image by appending additional least-significant bits to the image samples while downshift reduces bit depth by removing least-significant bits from the image samples, however making lossless compression impossible.

The interested reader can refer to the Blue Book [1] and the Green Book [2] of the Recommended standard for a more detailed description for the algorithm.

Fig. 2: System top-level block diagram, including data processing, control blocks and interconnection fabric.

3 CCSDS-122.1 SYSTEM-ON-CHIP ARCHITECTURE

The proposed System-On-Chip (SoC) architecture based on CCSDS-122.1-B-1 standard is shown in Fig. 2. The SoC targeted a Xilinx Zynq 7000 device, which includes two hardwired ARM programmable processor cores. One of the two ARM cores is utilized in our system as the main controller for clock sources initialization. It also provides system interface for debugging (USB, JTAG) and acts as a master device on the main AXI4-Lite bus system interconnection. System also includes the controller for the SpaceFibre (SpFi) interface and a number of AXI4-Lite/APB registers used by the processor to communicate with the compressor IP Cores.

The SoC architecture is build around three main hardware accelerator IP Cores that were developed and integrated in a data processing pipeline. The first part of the pipeline is an IP Core implementing the five-stage CDF 5/3 IWT spectral transform that operates in Band Interleave by Pixel (BIP) order. The last part of the pipeline is a CCSDS 122.0-B-2 IP Core that performs 2D compression (compatible with CCSDS 122.1) on the IWT-transformed data, which however operates in Band Sequential Order (BSQ) order. To bridge between the two different orderings, BIP and BSQ, a BIP2BSQ converter IP Core is placed in the middle of the pipeline that receives IWT-transformed data in BIP order and rearranges them into BSQ order suitable for the 2D encoder. To achieve it, the BIP2BSQ converter IP Core utilizes the external DDR3 memory to satisfy the large memory requirements, thus increasing the complexity of the implementation. Externally, the introduced architecture provides an AXI4-Stream input/output interface. Apart from these IP Cores, a custom rate-allocator method was also implemented in ARM embedded software that provides an effective rate-distortion/system resources/data-rate performance trade-off. In the following subsections, each of the three main IP Cores that were developed and constitute the CCSDS 122.1-B-1 data processing pipeline are described.

3.1 Five-stage CDF 5/3 IWT spectral transform

This IP Core implements the 5-level IWT 5/3 wavelet transform as it is specified in the CCSDS 122.1 standard. It receives a hyperspectral image in BIP (Band Interleaved by Pixel) format that is, it receives consecutively lines across the z-dimension of the input image in raster-scan order. There is no latency between the processing of two consecutive lines and the first pixel of the next line can be entered at the cycle right after the last pixel of the previous line was entered. This unit consists of 5 instantiations of a single-level IWT 5/3 unit which maps an input line to low and high frequency IWT coefficients. A concatenating unit is also used at the end in order to concatenate the 6 final resulting subbands into a single stream. The computations that take place are simple additions, subtractions and shifting operations and thus are implemented using FPGA LUTs without using DSP blocks. The implementation of the 5-level IWT 5/3 transform is fully compatible with the standard supporting all the edge cases that relate to different sequence sizes. Leveraging the input interface of two parallel 2 pixels (along the z-dimension), a 2 samples/cycle throughput performance is achieved. The IWT IP Core has been extensively validated using random test images and AVIRIS scenes from the CCSDS corpus of hyperspectral images. The maximum operating frequency on Zynq XC7Z045-FFG900 target device is 333.3 MHz.

3.2 CCSDS 122.0-B-2 2D Encoder

This IP Core implements the CCSDS 122.0 B-2 standard that defines a transformed-based compression algorithm for 2D images. It is an improved re-design of a previous implementation of CCSDS 122.0-B-1 already published at [3], with a more deep pipeline and a two pixel parallel input to increase maximum frequency and throughput performance. The architecture of the CCSDS 122.0 2D encoder IP Core can be divided into three main parts operating in parallel through pipelining: (a) the DWT 9/7M 2D transform and the storing of DWT coefficients as blocks in bitplane format, (b) the bitplane encoding (BPE) of the blocks including optimal code selection and subsequent entropy encoding and (c) the output packetization logic that produces the compressed stream. Note, that in the following, the focus is on the encoding of the AC coefficients which forms the bulk of the processing and the resources needed. The encoding of the DC coefficients and the encoding of the AC and DC depths are not discussed. They are performed in parallel to the encoding of the AC coefficients.

The DWT 9/7M transform unit can be configured to interface with 1 or 2 input pixels (coefficients) in parallel. This input interface is controlled through VHDL generics. When configured for 2 input pixels, a total throughput of 2 samples/cycle is achieved. Furthermore, input pixels may be signed or unsigned, configured again through VHDL generics. A more detailed description of the DWT architecture is presented in [4]. The DWT unit outputs 10 parallel subbands in total. These parallel streams are stored into intermediate FIFOs so that they can be rearranged into blocks (the notion of a 'block' is defined in the CCSDS 122.0 standard) and eventually be stored in bitplane format in the Segment Buffer implemented in Block RAM technology. A total of S (number of blocks per segment - fixed and equal to 128 in our implementation) blocks need to be stored in bitplane format into the Segment Buffer in order for BPE to take place. Double buffering of Segment Buffer allows efficient pipelining of DWT and BPE operations.

As soon as all 128 blocks of a segment are available (in bitplane format) in the Segment Buffer, the BPE unit, and in particular its subunit called BSMS (Block Scan and Map to Symbols), for each bitplane (starting from msb to lsb) fetches each raw 63-bit AC bitplane, corresponding to a block, from the Segment Buffer and maps it to stages 1,2,3,4 as described in the standard. Because these stages consist of variable length words, initially sparse words are produced accompanied by a corresponding valid mask and then these are converted into packed words accompanied by a length header. Also, these words are mapped to symbols as the standard describes. Then, for every 16 such processed 63-bit AC bitplanes (i.e. for every gaggle as defined in the standard) the optimum Code Option for each 2-bit, 3-bit, 4-bit symbol length is deduced by brute-force computing the total encoded length that corresponds to each such Code Option for the whole gaggle. Finally, after the best Code Option has been deduced, the symbols of stages 1,2,3 are passed to units called Entropy Encoders for entropy encoding. Note that at this stage, streams corresponding to stages 1,2,3,4 are parallel streams and have not been serialized into a single stream yet.

The final part of the introduced 2D encoder IP Core concatenates all stages along with header data, encoded DC coefficients and AC depths into a final compressed stream. Finally, the output codeword can be configured through VHDL generics to be either 32-bit or 64-bit to leverage the 2 parallel pixel inputs and increase the throughput performance. The CCSDS 122.0-B-2 design has been extensively validated using AVIRIS scenes from the CCSDS corpus of hyperspectral images using several lossless and rate-limited lossy compression configurations. The maximum throughput performance for these images, when configured with a 2 parallel input pixels per cycle input interface, is 1.7 samples/cycle. The maximum operating frequency achieved on Zynq XC7Z045-FFG900 target device is 200 MHz.

3.3 BIP2BSQ Converter

The BIP2BSQ IP Core converts the incoming hyperspectral cube from a BIP ordering following IWT based spectral decorrelation, to BSQ ordering and feeding the 2D encoder for compression. The converter utilizes the AXI4-Stream protocol in order to receive the decorrelated input image. The BIP2BSQ IP Core offers a unique approach where it distributes the reordered frames to more than one output stream in order to take advantage of parallelism in 2D compressors. For example, suppose that the available FPGA fabric allows for two 2D encoders to be instantiated in parallel. In that case, the BIP2BSQ IP Core will distribute the frames equally to each 2D encoder (the first 2D encoder will get all the even frames, and the second 2D encoder will get all the odd frames). When receiving the BIP data from the input AXI4 stream, the BIP2BSQ IP Core uses an internal BRAM packetizer which receives the incoming data from the AXI stream input and buffers them in a specific way to create more considerable burst lengths for the memory. Afterwards, the buffered data are transmitted to one or more Datamovers, responsible for sending the data to the memory through a Full AXI4 interface. An Write Address Generator generates the following destination address for the next write transaction for the Datamover. After completing the write transaction, the Datamover receives an acknowledgment through the write response Channel of the Full - AXI interface, signaling the completion of the transaction; if the transaction is successful, then an internal counter increases, which counts all the successful acknowledgments from memory. In the case of multiple Datamovers, the counters are summed in a specific way. Then, the result is sent to the Read Address Generator, which determines the number of in-line data available for fetching after performing internal calculations. For example, suppose the number of in-line data is greater or equal to a boundary (initially set to the read packet length, which is a generic configuration). In that case, the generator sends the Datamover the read address to retrieve the Read Packet Length number of data from memory. Afterwards, we wait until the following Read Packet Length data are in-line for fetching. The BIP2BSQ conversion has an inherent latency, being the performance bottleneck of the whole system limiting the entire system throughput to a value close to half. The BIP2BSQ IP Core is validated expensively using random hyperspectral cubes. The throughput performance is 2 cycles per sample and the achieved maximum frequency is 250MHz.

3.4 Rate allocation

The CCSDS 122.1 does not mandate any particular rate-allocation method allowing the users to choose any desired strategy to allocate a fixed bitrate budget among spectral transformed images, codes segments or subsets of coded segments. In the introduced CCSDS 122.1 implementation, a custom fixed rate allocation method is used as a trade-off between high-data rate performance at acceptable compression quality. In the proposed rate allocation method, the total target rate defined by the user is allocated to the frames of the IWT-transformed cube solely based on which of the six IWT subbands each frame belongs to. To do this, six fixed weights corresponding to the IWT subbands as described in annex F in CCSDS122.1 Blue Book [1] were used. In particular, each frame of the transformed cube is allocated a weighted percentage of the total target rate and finally each segment of a single frame is allocated uniformly a SegByteLimit. In practice, we used the formulation of the Reverse-Waterfill algorithm (described in Green Book [2]) and set the RAS parameter (Rate Allocation Subset, as defined in section 4 in Green Book [2]) large enough to hold the whole frame and set all segment variances to a constant value, thus making the SegByteLimit values depend only on the IWT weights. As a result, this rate allocation scheme outputs a total of 6 SegByteLimit values as a function of the user defined total target rate. In our implementation, these SegByteLimit values are computed by the ARM processor of the Zynq system and are then written to the AXI Lite configuration registers of the CCSDS122.0 IP Core and properly assigned to each frame of the spectral cube.

In Fig. 3, the rate-distortion performance for the AVIRIS scene 0 (*aviris_yellowstone_sc00*) is depicted comparing the proposed rate allocation scheme and the Reverse-Waterfill algorithm cited by the Recommended standard. In both cases the IWT spectral transform is assumed.

Fig. 3: Rate-distortion performance comparison for the *aviris_yellowstone_sc00* image

4 IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

Implementation results are shown in Table 1. The BRAM is the resource utilization bottleneck of the proposed CCSDS 122.1 system, dominated by the Segment Buffer of the CCSDS 122.0 2D encoder. Larger FPGA SoC devices (e.g. Zynq Ultrascale+ MPSoC FPGAs), applicable to CubeSat or New Space applications, could allow for more parallelism in 2D encoding by instantiating more CCSDS 122.0 IP cores, increasing throughput performance. It should be noted that the proposed CCSDS 122.1 architecture could be easily ported to Xilinx Radiation-Tolerant Kintex UltraScale XQRKU060 space-grade device which is suitable for institutional missions. On-board 1GB DDR3 RAM module was used to store intermediate results during image compression (BIP to BSQ transformation). The FPGA SoC had 3 clock domains, a) a 200MHz system clock domain where all the compression system related IP Cores operate along with the main AXI data interfaces buses, b) a 62.5MHz clock domain for the Gaisler SpFi core and c) a 667MHz clock domain for the ARM CPU core on the Zynq device. At 200MHz system clock, the achieved system internal data throughput performance (without taking into account the SpFi delay transmission) was measured during compression on the FPGA at 1.56Gbps. Total on-chip power consumption is estimated at 3.9W.

5 DESIGN VERIFICATION, VALIDATION AND DEMONSTRATION

The CCSDS 122.1 system was extensively verified using FPGA-in-the-loop verification. Validation and demonstration set-up was built around SpaceFibre interface to match space deployment. The demonstrator platform was based on a Xilinx Zynq-7000 SoC ZC706 Development Kit hosting a Zynq XC7Z045-FFG900 device along with an iSAFT Quad SpaceFibre PCIe interface card provided by TELETEL acting as EGSE. The iSAFT board was connected to ZC706 board through SFP+ to eSATA adapter. In order to establish the SpFi interface, the Cobham Gaisler SpFi IP Core was integrated

Fig. 4: Block diagram of the system validation and demonstration platform

Tab. 1: Resource utilization on the XC7Z045-FFG900 device.

Type	Total	Top level	% XC7Z045
LUT	218,600	45,170	20.66
FF	437,200	55,363	12.66
BRAM	545	436	80.09

on the FPGA system side. The demonstrator platform is depicted in Figure 4. The CCSDS 122.1 system functionality and throughput performance was successfully demonstrated by sending several test images from the EGSE PC to the CCSDS 122.1 system, over a 3.125Gbps link. Using the provided API software on the EGSE PC and software executed on the ARM core in the Zynq device, an automated test suite was implemented for system validation. AVIRIS hawaii sc01(614x512x224), maine sc10 (680x512x224) and yellowstone sc00 (680x512x224) images with different lossless and lossy compression configurations were used to validate the design. The received compressed hyperspectral images were successfully compared to golden responses produced by CNES CCSDS 122.1-B-1 golden reference model.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This works presents a hardware architecture and FPGA SoC implementation of the CCSDS 122.1 Recommended standard. The introduced hardware architecture was described in VHDL and implemented, validated and demonstrated on a commercially available Zynq-7000 SoC ZC706 Evaluation Kit development board hosting a Xilinx XC7Z045 SRAM FPGA achieving a throughput performance of 1.5 Gbps. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first hardware implementation of CCSDS 122.1-B-1 Recommended standard in the open literature. A hardware accelerated rate-allocation based on Reverse-Waterfill algorithm is under development to significantly improve the rate-distortion performance.

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